

SUN INVESTMENT ON EARTH

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Abstract:

We see the sky Sunrise, Sun set, Moon rise, Moon set with our eyes and also combined it through astrology with the help of ephemeris. Neutrino is an elementary particle in physics. Neutrino has no mass. Neutrino was discovered in 1956 by Cowan and Reines. Goldhaber discovered in 1958 that Neutrino has helicity (left hand habit). Indian scientists formed Indian Neutrino observatory in Pottipuram, Theni, Tamilnadu for research. Black dots on Sun make great changes in this earth.

Key Words: Sun Rise, Sun Set, Moon Rise, Moon Set, Related Astrology, Ephemeris, Neutrino, Elementary Particle, Physics, No Mass, Cowan And Reines, Goldhaber, Helicity, INO, Sun Transit Effects, Blackdots on Sun, Changes Universe.

Introduction:

We live on earth and below the Sun. We have seen Sun set, Sun rise, Moon set, Moon rise. Their timings are clearly given in ephemeris. Neutrino research is banned in Tamilnadu by politicians. Neutrino is an elementary particle in physics. They are teeny, tiny nearly massless particles that travel at near light speeds. Born from violent astrophysical events like exploding stars and gamma ray bursts, they are fantastically abundant in the universe, and can move as easily through lead as we move through air. But they are notoriously difficult to pin down. Neutrinos are really pretty strange particles when you get down to it, says John Conway a professor of physics at University of California, Davis. "They are almost nothing to all, because they have almost no mass and no electric charge. They're just little wisps of almost nothing". Ghost particles, they are often called. But they are one of the universe's essential ingredients and they have played an important role in helping scientists, understand some of the most fundamental questions in physics.

For example, if you hold your hand towards the Sunlight for one second, about a billion neutrinos from the Sun will pass through it, says Dan Hooper, a scientist at Fermi National Accelerator Laboratory and an associate professor of astronomy and astro physics at the University of Chicago. This is because they are shot out as a byproduct of nuclear fusion from the Sun that is the same process that produces Sunlight. They are important to our understanding of the kind of that go on in the Sun and also an important building block for the blueprint of nature", Hooper said. Particle physicists originally believed that Neutrinos were massless. But in the 1990's a team of Japanese scientists discovered that they actually have a smidgen of mass. This tiny bit of mass may explain why the Universe is made up of matter, not antimatter. Early in the process of Big Bang, there were equal amounts of matter and antimatters according to Conway "But the Universe expanded and cooled, matter and antimatter were mostly annihilated. We think Neutrinos may have something to do with that process. And it is a puzzle, why we are made out of matter and not antimatter.

Studying Neutrinos is difficult. They are tough to detect since they interact so weakly with other particles. But the newly completed Icecube Neutrino observatory will study Neutrinos inside a cubic kilometer block of ice in Antarctica. Here's how. When the Neutrinos interact with atoms inside the deep arctic ice detectors, they sometimes give off puffs of energy. "As Neutrinos pass through and interact, they produce charged particles, and the charged particles traveling through the ice give off light," Conway said. "That's how they're detected. It's like having a telescope for Neutrinos underground". Fermilab National Laboratory has an experiment that hurls a beam of Neutrinos 400 miles underground from Wisconsin to Northern Minnesota in about two milliseconds, and the lab is also planning a massive linear accelerator called Project X. That will study the sub atomic particles by sending them even farther. "If 100 years ago, I told someone that the universe was filled with no energy, I wonder if they would have believed you, Conway said. Who knows where we will be 100 years from now.

Neutrino's Helicity Habit:

Goldhaber, the scientist invented in 1958 that Neutrinos were left handed because they have negative helicity. So, weak interaction principle was developed.

Kinds of Neutrinos:

Electron belongs with lepton family. There are three leptons. Each has their wives.

No	Lepton	It's Wife
1	Electron	Electron Neutrino
2	Muon	Muon Neutrino

3	Taulepton	Taulepton Neutrino
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So, we can easily understand there are six types of neutrinos.

Indian Neutrinos Observatory:

INO is a particle physics research project under construction to primarily study atmospheric neutrinos in a 1200 meters (3,900 feet) deep cave under INO peak near Theni, Tamilnadu, India. It would be completed in the year 2015 at an estimated cost of Rupees 1,500 crores. The Government of Tamilnadu opposes this project because this project will affect local bio diversity and tiger species at Periyar Tiger Reserve and the Mathikettan shola National park in the Western Ghats between Tamilnadu and kerala border.

Time Calculation:

No	Name	Times	Time Duration
1	Eyeblink	2	1 Second
2	second	2	1 Tablet
3	Tablet	2	1 Guru
4	Guru	2	1 Soul
5	Soul	9	1 Sanikam
6	Sanikam	12	1 Vinazhi
7	Vinazhi	60	1 Nazhigai
8	Nazhigai	7½	1 Jamam
9	Jamam	4	1 Pozhuthu
10	Pozhuthu	2	1 Day
11	Day	30	1 Month
12	Month	12	1 Year
13	Year	60	1 Cycle
14	Year	17,28,000	1 Krutha era
15	Year	12,96,000	1 Thretha era
16	Year	8,64,000	1 Thvapara era
17	Year	4,32,000	1 Kali era

Planet's Light Takes Time to Reach the Earth:

1	Sun light takes	8.5	minutes to reach earth
2	Moon light takes	1.2	minutes to reach earth
3	Mars light takes	6.2	minutes to reach earth
4	Mercury light takes	2.3	minutes to reach earth
5	Jupiter light takes	4.3	minutes to reach earth
6	Venus light takes	4.2	minutes to reach earth
7	Saturn light takes	76	minutes to reach earth
8	Proxima centauri star takes	4	years to reach earth

Planets Taking Time to Revolve the Sun:

1	Mercury	87.97 Days
2	Venus	224.70 Days
3	Earth	365.256 Days
4	Mars	687.123 Days
5	Jupiter	11.86 Years
6	Saturn	29.46 Years

Planets Sidereal Rotation Period:

S.No	Planet	Time
1	Mercury	56 Days
2	Venus	243 Days (Anti Clock Wise)
3	Earth	23.56 Days
4	Mars	24.6 hrs.
5	Jupiter	9.8 hrs.
6	Saturn	10.4 hrs.
7	Sun	27 (Self rotation)

Details for Tamil Months Date, Nazhigai, Vinazhi and Sun Sign:

S.No	Month	Days	Nazhigai	Vinazhi	Sun Sign
1	Chitra	30	55	33	Aries
2	Visaga	31	24	12	Taurus
3	Aani	31	36	38	Gemini
4	Aadi	31	28	22	Cancer

5	Aavani	31	02	10	Leo
6	Purattasi	30	27	22	Virgin
7	Aippasi	29	54	07	Libra
8	Karthigai	29	27	24	Scorpio
9	Margazhi	29	20	53	Sagittarius
10	Thai	29	48	24	Capricorn
11	Masi	29	48	24	Aquaris
12	Panguni	30	20	21	Pisces

Name of Sun Rays, Its Number for Tamil Months:

S.No	Tamil Month	Name of Sunrays	Numbers of Rays
1	Chitra	Aanchan	7000
2	Visaga	Thootha	8000
3	Aani	Indiran	9000
4	Aadi	Suvitha	9000
5	Aavani	Vichuvan	9000
6	Purattasi	Pagan	11000
7	Aippasi	Parutsani	1000
8	Karthigai	Thoshta	8000
9	Margazhi	Mithran	7000
10	Thai	Vishnu	11000
11	Masi	Varunan	5000
12	Panguni	Poodan	1000

Journey of Sun towards North & South:

Sun starts his southward journey when he, enters cancer rasi (kadagam). Similarly he starts his Northward journey when he enters capricorn rasi (Thai, Magara sankranthi)

Black Dots in Sun:

Black dots in sun are called kethus. They are the sons of Rahu. They are called as Thamasakeelars. They are totally 33 dots. If they appear on solar corona they will affect the universe.

Dots and Results:

S.No	Dots in Solar Corona	Effects
1	Single dot	Famine
2	Two or more	King's death
3	white color	Suffers to Acharyas
4	Red color	Suffers to Police, Army men
5	Yellow color	Suffers to business man
6	Black dots	Suffer to labours

S.No	Image of Sun & Colour of Sun Rays	Effect
1	like pot	hunger & death
2	rays broken	death of king
3	Unvisible rays	fear of people
4	like entrance gate	danger to head quarters
5	like Umbrella	danger to country
6	like bow	war would come
7	black lines seen	king would be killed by minister
8	interfear through thunder or flash	death of king & other country king sworn
9	aura at sun rise or sun set	death of king & other country king sworn
10	looks like blood red colour	local war will increase
11	deer, donkey birds, young camel seen	People afraid.

Conclusion:

Without Sun we can't live on earth. Sun gives life to all Planets, Birds, Animals, Trees and human beings. The impact of the Sun is invaluable

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